

Aleksandra Mitrović, LL.M.,
Teaching Assistant,
Faculty of Law, University of Priština,
Temporary Head Office in Kosovska Mitrovica,
Republic of Serbia

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HERMENEUTIC SIGNIFICANCE OF THE SOCIOLOGICAL METHOD IN MODERN LAW

Abstract: *The goal of this scientific paper is to emphasize the theoretical and practical importance of the sociological method in the context of social challenges in legal practice and legal interpretation procedure. Given that law is an objective, spiritual and normatively shaped social phenomenon that has a temporal and spatial framework, it is not possible to ignore the social nature of law embodied in the constant influence of society on law and vice versa. In this paper, the starting point is the study of law, by observing the social reality and correlating the state and law to society as a whole or to individual social phenomena. In that context, the sociological method provides for a better, more concise, more efficient legal interpretation, taking into account the complete social situation that is regulated by law, and examines the dominant social interests that law is guided by. Therefore, law can only be explained if man is understood as a being who has social consciousness and who is subject to social discipline. If a human being has social awareness, he/she distinguishes law from force. Considering that order cannot be maintained only through consciousness and moral factors, force is a necessary element for the enforcement of law and the establishment of social peace. Finally, as the complex nature of law calls for an integral approach to study, it generates a complementary hermeneutic relationship of the normative and the sociological methods in order to explain the causes of partial or complete (non)implementation of legal principles*

*aleksandra.mitrovic@pr.ac.rs, ORCID ID 0000-0003-1150-6907

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in contemporary law and society alike. Bearing in mind the delicate, dynamic and unstable nature of law, the conclusion is that the hermeneutic approach to legal principles, both in legal theory and in legal practice, cannot exist without the application of the sociological method as the only one that manages to ensure sufficiently systematic and empirical investigation of laws applicable in social interactions.

Keywords: *sociological method, legal principles, law, society, legal practice.*

1. Hermeneutic Significance of Sociological Analysis of Law – Sociological Positivism

Sociological analysis of law considers two important elements of law: substance (social relations), and structure (legal norms). A more precise systematization of the social nature of law is not possible because the complex nature of the phenomenon of social relations bears the characteristic of *ars inventoriae*, which implies a constant creation of new and a constant change of existing *topos* (Visković, 1997: 83). Therefore, the sociological analysis of law examines the substance and the structure of law in an integral way, taking into account the variable social nature of law. If law were to be viewed as an exclusively social phenomenon, social relations become a materialized substrate of law, including those that create a negative effect, such as social conflicts; hence, social existence affects law by taking the form of a legal norm. On the other hand, if law were viewed as a normative system, we would not be able to approach a more detailed sociological analysis of law at all. Therefore, the social nature of law requires a sociological aspect of analysis, to investigate the impact of law on society but also the impact of society acts on law.

The sociological approach to law is based on observing the mutual relationship between law and society, as well as emphasizing the sources, goals and functions that law has in society. In this sense, three essential elements of law are defined: social relations, values, and norms as constituent elements and at the same time sources of law. Thus, social relations are also material sources of law, legal values are value-based (ethical) sources of law, while legal norms are formal sources of law (Visković, 1981: 83). Yet, the subject matter of lawyers' involvement may be only those social relations that entail public control and physical coercion and contain a conflict of interests that threatens the existing social systems (Visković, 1981: 94). Conflicts that arise in those relationships, aimed at satisfying the basic natural and social needs and (biological, economic, political) interests of man, are crucial for social systems.

As a specific social phenomenon, the study of law requires an integral approach, which entails the study of law as a social reality in two ways: internally i.e. substantively (studying the substance, the content of law), and externally i.e. structurally (studying the constitutive elements of the legal norm). As the value aspect of the law is reserved for the philosophy of law, the law as a normative order subjected to the state has a monopoly of coercion, thus creating an additional opportunity for the sociological method to analyze the normative nature of law; being a form of social control by the state, law will be analyzed as a spiritual, normatively framed phenomenon. The sociological analysis looks at law as the relationship between the state and law, where the law is partly related to the state and its mechanisms of coercion through legal norms. The analysis of law in this narrower sense observes legal norms as a means of forced settlement of conflicts in pre-normative legal relations to achieve the essential interests and goals of ruling groups. Values and goals highlighted in legal norms are protected by coercion; legal actions that are favorable to the ruling group are designated as obligations and powers, and those that are not favorable are designated as misdemeanors or sanctions in case of non-fulfillment of obligations (Visković, 1981: 162-163).

In this context, we may examine some of the foundations of the theoretical-methodological platform about legal phenomena emphasizing the importance of social factors in the creation and application of legal norms. To shed more light on the social aspect of the law, Prof. Đorđe Tasić looked critically at the sociological positivism of Léon Duguit, which paved the way for disclosing the truth in legal theory. In this sense, sociological positivism leads to a reaction that results in idealism; such reaction which could only deepen positivism, which was preceded by rationalism; and positivism was more elastic and moderate than rationalism, but without changing its foundations, object, and methods of analyzing society and law. It focused on man as a social being (a member of society). In this regard, state bodies are not there to operate as they wish but to achieve certain social goals, by abiding by the Constitution and social law (Tasić, 1928: 433).

If we carefully analyze Duguit's position, i.e. the view that any man, as a citizen, could refuse to obey the law passed by the state if he did not want to, referring to social law. However, according to Duguit, as every person is aware of the relationship between the values of the hierarchy in society, there is an imperative need for the work of public services in the society-state. Therefore, Duguit only theoretically approves of the citizens' to resist the state government. As social life does not tolerate anarchy, resistance is allowed only to the extent where social peace is undisturbed. Based the above, Prof. Đorđe Tasić concludes that Duguit's notion of social law, as well

as normative awareness, is imbued with the idea of order. However, as order cannot be maintained only via awareness and moral factors, it recognizes force as a necessary element for enforcing rights and establishing social peace (Tasić, 1928: 435).

“Law cannot be explained in any way if a man is not understood as a being who has social awareness and is thus subject to social discipline. Only a socially aware being can distinguish law from force, and from other social norms and regulations, such as moral ones (Tasić, 1928: 435). The state is, therefore, designated as the creator of law (positive law), while state bodies are there to perform social tasks. However, being determined as logical legality only by the current interests of the ruling group, state (positive) law is not the best law. Duguit points out that the state has only one goal: to establish the legal order of the state (state law). This kind of law ignores natural law, which must not be excluded in the process of creating laws; one can speak of human law only if natural law is present in positive law, i.e. the law that serves not only the state but all people. Therefore, the sociological analysis points out that the creation of positive law requires the participation of the norms of natural law because only such law will be based on a rational conception of the authority of the mind, and not the authority of force (sanctions). Combining all three elements of law calls for an integrated approach because we see the law as “a system of state and social norms by which the most important and conflicting interpersonal relations are forcibly directed to achieve peace, security, justice and other dominant values” (Visković, 2001: 117).

“As for sociologists, supporters of collective consciousness would like to give precedence to the idea of peace because to preserve the dominance of solidarity (which they regard above all) in the society governed by the idea of differentiation and growing social entanglements, it is necessary to give special importance to the will for peace, agreement, compromise, and mutual concessions” (Tasić, 2002: 80). Therefore, in the hermeneutics of law, it is not possible to leave out social factors as essential elements of interpretation; namely, “giving importance to social factors is necessary because the law is created to achieve appropriate effects through its application, to regulate and stabilize social relations appropriately” (Stanković, 1998: 3). If a clear distinction were made between law in the narrower and broader sense, the conclusion would be that state law is strictly formalized and precisely determined, while social law is based on the idea of social solidarity and integration but also social conflict, i.e. on a non-unified interpretation. In this context, when analyzing Durkheim’s idea, society is defined as a “hearthstone of ideals” that guarantees spiritual life, because society is not a body organized according

to the model of an organism and its vital functions, as he says: “In that body lives one soul; it is a set of collective ideals” (Tasić, 1927/1928: 144).

Finally Tasić concludes that ideals do not escape natural explanation, but are viewed like all social phenomena because ideals also originated in nature and from nature. Society in this sense, as Durkheim states, should be understood as a *sui generis* concept because it has the power to produce ideals for individuals, imposes its coercion, and puts itself in the role of a legislator who demands respect and obedience, and as a such society can also be understood as a lofty moral personality and collective will. Analyzing this point of view of Durkheim “postulates human society” as Kant postulates God (Tasić, 1927/1928: 145).

While Tasić believes that collective consciousness, a social reality that acquires the contours of a supreme moral personality and collective consciousness as such, does not exist, Duguit sees it more objectively and figures with public services, which is a far more positivist position than the one that advocates the notion of a sovereign collective personality of social reality.

Finally, Kant does not start from the nature of man, but from freedom itself. Kant believes that “freedom is not given, but determined” by law, while Kant sees law itself as a set of laws for which external legislation is possible. Kant distinguishes between external and internal legislation. With a hermeneutic approach, Kant separates *legality* – external legislation (members of a state are kept in the community), from *morality* – internal (ineligible characters of people).

2. The Role of the Sociological Method in Legal Interpretation

As there is dissonance between normative and actual, that is, ideal and real, to detect such differences that cause such dissonance, sociological method is required that detects the norm as a social reality, where the legal norm is an ideal scenario, thus, it is necessary for the legal method to participate in the procedure of research. By detecting differences between the actual social reality and the law determined by legal dogma, a task is given to the sociological method to determine where these differences are coming from.

As an empirical method, sociological method explores human legal consciousness when considering written as well as unwritten law. Differences between social reality and written law, as the task of a sociological method is not very difficult since it is easy to see the difference between written law and the law presented in social reality. It is much more difficult to spot the difference between unwritten law and the law existing in human mind, that

is, common law. In this case there is a common rule everybody knows and keeps in mind, but still people behave contrary to what they know and what they have in their mind as unwritten norm. Sociological method sees the difference existing as valid (written) and actually valid, that is, the one that is applied. Procedures followed by the sociological method in research of the law are not significantly different from general procedures of sociological research – they are simply the application of general procedures to the law (Šušnjić, 1973: 307-319). If the sociological method would be excluded from the procedure of law interpretation, the law would be observed as absolutely ideal concept existing outside of space and time, independent, without its beginning and the end, without the cause of occurrence, without the purpose of existence and in this sense, without significance. However, the sociological method cannot provide answers to all questions, such as the content of legal norm and the issue of normative elements comprising the norm, thus the normative method always precedes the sociological method hence the sociological method defines its domain of study in a more precise manner. After the norm becomes known, its link to the society is examined, that is, realistic factors of norm's content, which is the subject of sociological research. When the legal method learns the content of the legal norm, the sociological method explores why the content of a legal form is as it is, specifically, how is it reflected on the social cohesion. Legal norm has its role in the social function, in the accomplishment of a certain social goal, and this speaks of the social impact to the content of the norm, and the norm to the society. This relation is explored by the sociological method, and which social factors formed the content of the legal norm, and how the norm impacts the society considering full social situation regulated by the law, and then, investigating what are the dominant social interests applied by the law, in an effort to reach the actual meaning of the legal norm. In this sense, the law is a "system of state and social norms that forcefully direct the most important and the most conflicting human interactions to accomplish peace, security, justice and other socially dominant values" (Visković, 2001: 117). Therefore, the structure of a legal norm will not be defined by a logical design, but the necessity, relationship between the powers, goals of the society. Social relationship formed by norms becomes, therefore, a positive law including all aforementioned substrates of social cohesion.

The law that has an *a priori* character, to get the positive legal affirmation, must pass *a posterior* filter of justice thus getting its positive legal materialization. In this way, the law becomes matter and ceases being a theory since its concretization replaces abstract, imagination is replaced by realization through case law, enabling the law to prove and show it's *a posterior* nature using empirical statement of case law.

The process of detecting true meaning of legal norm is the procedure in which the interpreter cannot be free in adopting final decision because if we use the example of judicial regulation, the judge will not be essentially different from any individual, but, his action will be backed by the factual monopoly of enforcement, that is, the state. The judge, in this sense, as any other citizen, has its own view of things when it comes to the interest of the law to protect. However, the procedure of interpretation and application of the law by legal practitioners (judges) starts with the process of collecting and processing facts, followed by classification and determination of the same with the goal of reaching the final decision. After fact processing that is implemented through the process of court expertise, the process of connecting facts follows that is performed based on the estimate of significance of facts for the given case to be resolved. Connecting and assessment, as well as interpretation of facts can only be done using the method of sociological conclusion drawing used by judges in decision making. Each judge certainly knows or feels to what extent relevant experience is important to adopt a court decision (Rüthers, 1999: 377), in order to finalize court proceedings. Since the criteria of interpretation is within the mind of the interpreter, as Hasemer considered (Rüthers, 2009: 253-283), even in routine cases, the judge must be careful in adopting decisions and must be aware decisions made will impact human destiny. Decision of the court therefore cannot be free; it is necessary to establish method in this freedom to avoid arbitrariness. The judge, as an interpreter, is obligated to consider all circumstances of the given social atmosphere and stick to the opinion of the creator of legal norm during its creation, as pointed out by A. Boeckh, constant research of author's words is necessary (Boeckh, 1977: 11). True meaning of legal norm must, therefore, be limited with given language and logical interpretation, so the judge, before adopting the final decision, acts within certain limits. In case the judge considers that the law does not protect the interest it should protect, the judge is obligated never to cross the limits set through his arbitrary opinion. Only in case when the decision is adopted with just cause and with sufficient purpose, we may speak of justice that is aligned with current value dynamics of the system of a society that is adequately harmonized with the dynamics of legal interpretation.

The task of the sociological method is to find out how much normative law is more socially accurate, how much legal norms are present in society. It is a method that deals with the observation and research of real phenomena, which is, among other things, human behavior and its related actions among people, i.e. the relationship of human reactions to the presented model of behavior through the norm. When comparing what is stated as a model (rule) of behavior in the legal norm, and the legal awareness of the person about

that stated rule, one comes to a very common situation, which is the existence of inconsistencies between what should be (rights and obligations in legal norm) and what is (legal consciousness of a person, i.e. how a person reasons and accepts what is presented to him as a model or rule of conduct). Thus, there is a discrepancy between the normative and the real, that is, the ideal and the real. In order to reveal those differences that cause disharmony, the participation of the sociological method is necessary, which reveals the norm as a social reality, where the legal norm is at the same time an ideal phenomenon, and it is necessary that the legal method also participates in the research process.

3. Hermeneutics of the correspondence of the Sociological Method and the Normative Method in the process of interpreting the legal norm

The legal norm is recognized as a factual element of law, but so it is not the most important from a more moderate sociological point of view. The existence of a legal norm is affirmed by its materialization in the form of actions through practice, but not as assertions in the abstract sense through theory. Both in the interpretation within the framework of legal theory, i.e. hermeneutics, and in the interpretation within the framework of legal practice, the importance of the sociological method in the interpretation of the legal norm is exceptional because it enables a better, more precise, clearer and more thorough understanding of the law and the meaning of the legal norm, as well as a more effective influence on society, and more effective application in society (state). Even though it is present in different areas of legal interpretation, the application of social method differs in the area of discovering the law and in the area of legal method. The area of discovering the law demands a two-fold role of the sociological method, thus, for the detection of certain social side of the law it shall be applied individually, while in the legal method it can be used as auxiliary method with the normative one or any other method in the procedure of creating and applying law, when it is complementary jointed with other methods).

Process of creating and preparing the law are a matter of case law that “may be studied from different aspects, for example, when exploring the impact of different social factors to decision making of judges, when we question how a sociological expertise (knowledge sociology provides on the society) impacts application of the law, when we explore the place of judiciary within the system of division of power, when we explore social features within the judicial class and its impact to decision making, when, from a subjective, actually social – psychological position, we direct our attention to other par-

ticipants in the judicial procedure (parties in litigation, victims of a crime, perpetrators, jurors, plaintiffs, defendants) etc.” (Bovan, 2014: 117). It is necessary for the court proceedings, as well as sociology of law, to apply knowledge that has been gained by applying sociological method, since this enables detection of social, psychological, cultural and natural factors that impact the procedure of creation and application of law. In this sense, it can be said that “sociology of law is a special sociology that explores the interaction between the society and the law”. Sociology of law is pretty abstract and undefined, imprecise to say the least. In literature we can find it in different variations, thus, for example, it is said that the sociology of law studies social side of the law, the law as a social concept, social basis of the law, impact of the society to the law, etc.” (Bovan, 2004: 109-120). The procedure of creating a legal norm, that is, creating positive law implies application of tradition and natural law since the natural law is universal, timeless, ever-present, immanent, for all humans and knows no limitations in territorial, racial, religious sense. Natural law, therefore, knows no classes since it is super-national, super-positive, original and it serves justice and mankind, not injustice and autocracy.

Finally, it is important to point out that the positive law ideologically always relies on the natural law to be considered a law beneficial for a country, that is, a society. It can be said that the law is nothing else than justified reason for people to act, that is, the society to react to authoritarian rules branded as legal norms. Social interactions are therefore consequence of authoritarian character of rules presented in legal norms. With this, one should stipulate necessity of existence of reason (rules – legal norms) otherwise the social life would be in defect (Coleman, Himma, Shapiro, 2004: 15).

In this context, legal norms must be aligned with social changes regardless of whether they are a result of evolution or revolution. In addition to legal norms, moral norms are also subjected to certain level of transformation (Perović, 1975: 163), since moral norms essentially follow the variability of social cohesion set in time and space since the “time and space are most obvious concepts; thus, they are never disputed” (Lukić, 1992: 54). Space (place) and time are, as Kant points out, *a priori* concepts without which it is impossible to deliberate on the world, since the time is a measure of duration, existence of things, phenomena and the world. In this concept, the procedure of creating legal norms, that is, creating positive law implies the application of tradition and natural law since the natural law is universal.

Therefore, the natural law does not recognize classes since it is super-national, super-positive, original and it serves justice and mankind, not injustice and autocracy. Finally, it is important to point out that the positive law ideologi-

cally always relies on the natural law to be considered a law beneficial for a country, that is, a society. In this sense Tasić points out: "Regarding positive law, whatever type it is, it cannot be imagined without social discipline and will, where both are understood as complex and variable concepts. There is a special form of discipline or peaceful will, which means to know how to compromise your own interests and benefits or know how to be tolerant to the opinion of others, in general interest and in the interest of a new legal order. AAA of ideals... This is true idealism" (Tasić, 2002: 81). Also, Tasić states: "Compromise understood in such a way bears the characteristics of solidarity that, after mitigating the strict character of the demand, paves the way for a more solid solidarity" (Tasić, 2002: 81). The best example of the law as social phenomenon is the positive law as purely social creation since it is applied among people (society), it exists within the minds of men and regulates their behavior. Therefore, the law cannot be observed only as a normative, or ideal notion that exists on its own and only for its own benefit since the law exists among the people, in their minds, and for the people. The example of creating legal norm, when the creator of legal norm must consider the fact it is part of the society, part of certain social culture, part of current law, thus the law continues on the creator in positive or negative sense in the process of norm creation, it is clear to what extent and in what way the law is connected to the society. This is the reason why studying law demands the application of not only normative, but also the sociological method.

As such, sociological method in law has been created based on two completely different perspectives on the society, with, on one hand, we have consensual sociological theories – in which the society is based on and maintained on the basis of organic solidarity or interest – agreement on values (consensus) among people, while on the other side we have conflicting sociological theories in which it is proven that the society is based and maintained by forced regulation of interest and value conflicts among the members of unequal ruling and non-ruling social classes and layers (Jogan, 1978). Since the subject of research always determines the methods of research (Visković, 1980: 3), studying law entails all theoretical settings and technical procedures enabling cognition, as well as practical processing of specific and necessary subject of experience of legal scholars (Visković, *ibid.*).

Considering the social side of the law, sociological analysis of the law in theory and in practice applies the sociological method in get results as precise as possible. Sociological method may, therefore, in studying law, find its application in legal theory – science, and in legal practice – operation of judiciary. In both cases it explores the sociological context of the law, where in first case this is done in an abstract, and in the second case in a specific,

empirical manner. The term “sociological method” is just a common name for a larger number of different theories on the composition and dynamics of social phenomena that are serves a hypothesis for further learning and practical processing of social phenomena in general and separate legal concepts, where there is also a difference between sociological procedures and exploration methods (Gilli, 1974). Sociology, therefore, cannot study the law using only one method, here we are talking about the application of a large number of different methods to fully investigate the complex, dynamic and variable social essence of the law, based on cause and effect. This is why sociological method is included in the group of cause-and-effect methods that empirically study the law determining causal and also non-causal rules (functional, developmental, etc.) of the law as concepts that cause action (Lukić, 1965: 35). “Since the goal of science is acquiring knowledge, the scientific method is an element internal structure of science that shows us how is the knowledge reached, that is, how scientific activity is developed and performed” (Bovan, 2014: 18). Finally, the method includes elements that are of significant importance for acquiring new knowledge in science, as well as verification of acquired knowledge.

“The structure of the scientific method includes three elements: theoretical, technical and logical. A method is very often equalized with one of stated elements in literature. Most frequently, the method is aligned with its technical element when the method entails only different techniques of collecting and processing data (these techniques are mostly called scientific method in a narrow sense)” (Gilli, 1974). These are the tools that may be used to learn a subject, that is, specified procedures, as well as assets used to detect features of the subject that is the goal of scientific research (Lukić, 1975: 47-48). A good portion of modern legal theory opposes separation of any method that is applied in research of legal and other social phenomena. In this manner, sociological and normative method are connected and are mutually complementary and presupposed, even though essentially they are different since one of them is realistic and the other one idealistic, still, they are complementary and share the same function. This is quite justified and understandable since the law is an ideal and realistic notion that exists to achieve certain social goals. Since the normative method is unable to study law as isolated spiritual creation, outside of time and space, it must consider social elements of the law in addition to its normative structure. The normative method fails to scientifically explain the law and the interaction between the law and the society in full, so the role of the legal method is more of a descriptive nature with the ability to merely describe the law. The essence is reached only with complementary action of the sociological method, since it is necessary to detect social causes of occurrence of the law, and then determine the role

of the law in society and vice-versa. The only successful method for this is the sociological method that will be applied when the law is observed is a narrower sense (sum of legal norms). Sociological method shall, therefore, endeavor to determine the law as a norm that occurs under the impact of a number of social phenomena. The sociological method deals with issues related to social powers impacting creation of certain legal norms and their interpretation as normatively arranged interests represented by dominant social groups. As the normative method fails to provide answers to questions related to social causes leading to creation, interpretation and application of legal norms as formal social will, it is necessary to apply complementary joint action of sociological method in the procedure of legal interpretation).

Among others, the interpretation of the law cannot be envisaged without the application of normative and sociological method that must be mutually complemented and presupposed.

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Александра Митровић,
Асистент,
Правни факултет, Универзитет у Приштини
са привременим седиштем у Косовској Митровици,
Република Србија

ХЕРМЕНЕУТИЧКИ ЗНАЧАЈ СОЦИОЛОШКОГ МЕТОДА У САВРЕМЕНОМ ПРАВУ

Резиме

Циљ овог научног рада је да истакне теоријски и практичан значај социолошког метода пред друштвеним изазовима правне праксе и поступку правне интерпретације. Како је право објективна духовна и нормативно уобличена друштвена појава која поседује временски и просторни оквир, није могуће занемарити социјалну природу права присутну кроз константан утицај друштва на право и обрнуто. Полазиште овог рада је проучавање права уз уважавање друштвене стварности тако што се држава и право доводе у везу са друштвом у целини или појединим друштвеним појавама. Социолошки метод у том контексту, омогућава квалитетнију, концизнију, ефикаснију правну интерпретацију узимајући у обзир комплетну друштвену ситуацију коју право регулише и испитује доминантне друштвене интересе којима се право води. Дакле, право се једино може објаснити ако се човек схвати као биће које има социјалну свест и које је подвргнуто социјалној дисциплини. Стога, ако је човек биће које има социјалну свест, то уједно значи да разликује право од силе. Будући да се ред не може одржати само путем свести и моралних чинилаца, сила је нужан елемент за спровођење права и успостављање социјалног мира. Најзад, како сложена природа права захтева интегрални приступ проучавања, то резултира комплементаран херменеутички однос нормативног и социолошког метода како би се објаснили узроци делимичног или потпуног (не)остварења правних принципа како у савременом праву, тако и у друштву. Имајући у виду деликатну, динамичну и несталну природу права, закључак је да се херменеутички приступ правним принципима како у правној теорији, тако и у правној пракси, не може замислити без примене социолошког метода јер он једини успева да довољно систематично и емпиријски истражи функционалне законе права у друштвеним интеракцијама.

Кључне речи: социолошки метод, правни принципи, право, друштво, правна пракса.

